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THE ESSENCE OF ANTHROPOGONIC MYTHS OBSERVED IN AZERBAIJANI FOLKLORE

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СУЩНОСТЬ АНТРОПОГОНИЧЕСКИХ МИФОВ В АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНСКОМ ФОЛЬКЛОРЕ

Abstract.

The ancient way of thinking, creative thinking about the emergence of the first people was described in different ways in different peoples. The existence of differences of these types is natural and is due to the fact that each society has its own religious beliefs, philosophical views and mythical ideas. Like all the peoples of the world, the ancient Azerbaijanis were one of the founders of these types of texts, which formed the basis of mythology. In some myths of the Azerbaijani Turks dedicated to the miraculous creation of the first human not mentioning the concrete names and using the words "the first human" or "human being" are observed. But in parallel, in most anthropogonic myths, it is also observed that the first human was miraculously attached to the name of Father Adam, created from the soil by the judgment of Allah.

Аннотация.

Древние представления о появлении первых людей, творческом способе мышления описывались по-разному у разных народов. Существование таких различий естественно и обусловлено тем, что каждое общество имеет свои уникальные религиозные верования, философские взгляды и мифические представления. Как и все народы мира, древние азербайджанцы были в числе создателей подобного рода текстов, составивших основу мифологии. В некоторых мифах азербайджанских турков, посвященных чудесному созданию первого человека, конкретное имя не упоминается, а используются слова «ilk insan»/«первый человек» и «insanoglu»/«инсаноглу». Однако параллельно большинство антропогонических мифов также связывают первого человека с именем Адама, который был чудесным образом создан из земли по велению Бога.

Keywords: *Azerbaijani folklore, Anthropogonic myths, genesis, first human, first people, Adam and Eve, soil*

Ключевые слова: *Азербайджанский фольклор, антропогонические мифы, сотворение мира, первый человек, первые люди, Адам и Ева, земля*

Introduction. In science there are anthropogonic (origin) myths about the emergence of human, which are considered as an archaic phenomenon of thought and creativity, formed a long time ago. Later it became an important element of individual epic texts, becoming a manifestation of artistic thinking about the formation of a conscious living being, the first man or the first human couple. Later it became an important element of individual epic texts, becoming a manifestation of artistic thinking about the formation of a conscious living being, the first human or the first human couple. The ancient way of thinking, the creative thinking about the first people is described differently in various peoples. The existence of differences of this type is natural and it is inevitable that each society has its own religious beliefs, philosophical views and mythical ideas. As all the peoples of the world, the ancient Azerbaijanis were one of the founders of this type of texts, which formed the basis of mythology. In some myths of the Azerbaijani Turks dedicated to the miraculous creation of the first human not mentioning the concrete names and using the words "the first human" or "human being" are

observed. But in parallel, in most anthropogonic myths, it is also observed that the first human was miraculously attached to the name of Father Adam, created from the soil by the judgment of Allah.

Studying the national folklore texts, it turns out that, according to the ancient ideas, the creation of the first human is associated with the soil. These imaginations, which have no alternative, do not negate the motif of the human's descent from trees, various animals (e.g. wolf, bear), birds – the imaginations of the miraculous births. These substances are not observed in the texts of the anthropogonic myths belonging to the Azerbaijani people. They are often found in our fairy tales and epics.

According to mythological ideas, it is no coincidence that the creation of Adam and Eve, considered the first people, is exactly associated with the soil, which is a symbol of fertility. For Azerbaijani Turks, who say "Göyün yeddi qatı var; birinci qat torpaxdı ki, qara camaat yaşayır" (Translation: "The sky has seven layers; the first layer is the soil/earth, where the poor people live") (Azerbaijani mythological texts, 1988:

35), as mentioned, the sanctity of the soil is the main point. The saying “be fertile like the soil”, which is addressed to humans, also mentions being a symbol of fertility. In national folklore – anthropogonic myths collected from the people, along with the land, the water also protects its sacredness.

If we consider the anthropogonic myths archaically as a continuation of cosmogonic myths, then the connection of human origin with the elements of land or water seems logically reasonable. This type of text series – the stories explaining mythical concepts – completely deliver the whole existence of the human, the miraculous realization of his birth into the world. Azerbaijani mythological texts, the main essence of which is the concept of creation, are the investigation object of this article.

From the scientific literatures it becomes clear that the motif of the miraculous birth itself is also one of the motifs that go back to the myths about the emergence of the first people, i.e., the anthropogonic myths. As an example, one can show the myths about Adam and Eve. They exist in the oral literature of many peoples and form the main leitmotif of the texts about the creation. In general, despite the fact that various motifs are described in relation to the first people, the genesis texts about this topic are mainly connected with the name of Adam and Eve. In fact, the content of creation texts also contains the content of birth, but the symbolic birth.

The texts with symbolic birth content are notable precisely in the anthropogonic myths that are found in the folklore of the Azerbaijani Turks. In one of these texts it is said: *“Lap qabaqlar Allahdan başqa heç kim yoxuymuş. Yer üzü də başdan-başa suyuymuş. Allah bu suyu lil eliyir, sonra da lili qurudub torpax eliyir... Torpaxdan palçıx qəyirib insanları yaradır, onlara uruh verir”* (Translation: *“Before, there was no one except Allah. The Earth was water from the beginning to the end. Allah made this water silt and then dried the silt and made it soil... Allah made mud from the soil and created people, giving them souls”*) [Fables, legends and rumors, 26]. In another text, although the symbolic motif of birth is preserved, the cause of creation depends on the power of other beings: *“Günəş və Ayın izdivacından törəmiş 364 ötüycənin sonbeşiyi dəryaya baxarkən gördüyü qəribə bir əks onu təəcübləndirir. Sonra bunun öz əksi olduğunu anlayaraq çal-çamurdan (torpaqdan) özünə oxşar iki əcaib məxluq düzəldir... Elə o gündən də ötüycənin palçıqdan düzəltdiyi qəribə məxluqlar bir-birilərini Adəm-Həvvə deyər çağırırlar”* (Translation: *The latest one of 364 great-great-grandchildren born from the marriage of the Sun and the Moon, while looking at the sea was surprised by a strange reflection. Then, realizing that it was his own reflection, he made two strange creatures similar to himself from the soil... From that day the strange creatures, that the great-great-grandson made from clay, call each other Adam and Eve*) [Gazakh examples, 18]. In the first text, the Allah-human relationship, the participation of auxiliary forces in this relationship and thus the conscious participation of Allah in creation, presupposes the idealistic explanation of the issue. The primitive era creative worldview of the people of the region clears up the essence of beliefs. In other words,

the anthropogonic myths about the human creation, which are artistic manifestations, are also common in Azerbaijan and coincide in some moments with the contents of world folklore and in some moments acquire a specific character. According to the second text, the mission of creation is undertaken by the Sun's great-great-grandson.

Despite the fact that the first source of the motif Adam and Eve known to the science is considered to be the Bible (a collection of sacred books of Christianity), one can observe it in the other holy book “The Holy Quran” [the Holy Quran, 57]. It is important to remember these phrases: *“Indeed, the example of Jesus in the sight of Allah is like that of Adam. He created him from dust, then said to him, “Be!” And he was!”* [the Holy Quran, 57]. In the folklore of some Turkic peoples, Adam and Eve are replaced by completely other heroes (for comparison, it is enough to characterize Torungoy and Eje in the Altai myths and Er-Sogotakh according to the yakut Turks, who remembered as “this is also as Adam” [Ogel 2006:113]), however, the names of these images are not found among the mythological texts of the Azerbaijani Turks. According to B.Ogel's thought, the ancient Turks called the first human Yalnguk and the son of a human as the son of Yalnguk [Ogel, 2006:471]. The stone inscriptions belonging to the Sumerians, echoing with clay tablets within the ancient sources investigated, also provide valuable information in this context. According to the Bible, if the first man who appeared in the world is associated with the name of Adam, one of the male sexes, the ancient Sumerian myths tell about other information: “The first human was named Lulla, who was created in the image of a goddess, a woman. Her gender was female and she was formed from the soil, so she was called a part of the soil or the mother goddess” [Vardiman, 1990: 18].

In one of the folklore texts collected from the territory of Azerbaijan it is described that Allah first created the seas, animals and plants living in the waters and then decided to create a beautiful, unique creature that stands above all these creatures living on the Earth: *“Allah Almighty sends Gabriel to the Earth to create human and orders him to bring a handful of the soil from there. When the Earth learns the idea of Allah from Gabriel, he says: “Oh my Allah! If the person You want to create from a handful of the soil that you have taken from me make sins, he won't be saved from the hell. But I have no strength to burn in the fire of hell. For Your sake, don't create this existence!” Gabriel does not take the soil and returns back. But later Michael and Israfil come to the Earth to take a handful of soil. The Earth begs them both and they return without touching the soil. Finally, Azrael is sent to the Earth again. The Earth again begs him a lot. But Azrael answers so: “All that you say is true, but the command of Allah must be done”. He takes a handful of soil and returns. As Azrael performed this task with skill, he was told to take the lives of people on the verge of death”* [Southern Azerbaijan folklore, 2013:17].

On the basis of the examples it is confirmed once again that there are interesting texts about the origin of human in national folklore and those texts describe the

miraculous origin of human. These images have been transformed from the myths into the epic folklore genres. According to Azerbaijani folklore, the oldest of the first miraculously formed human, as it is mentioned, is sometimes presented under the special names; it means, the names Adam and Eve given to the heroes, resonate with the known characters of other peoples of the world. These miraculous beings, created from the soil by the judgment of Allah, are the manifestation of the mythical worldview. As it is mentioned, the other Turkic peoples have also many myths with this theme. The main characters of the folklore examples dedicated to the creation of the first human are known with the names Eje and Torongay, Er-Sogotakh. According to the folklore texts, Allah also created them from a handful of soil. As their birth was miraculous, their mastery of the mechanism of giving birth to the child was also in an unusual way.

The archaic heroes who sinned by eating the forbidden fruit were given birth pains as a punishment. Let's pay attention to some specific examples of those born from the first people. In one of the texts it is said that during 72 years Mother Eve each time gave birth to the twins - a boy and a girl. They gave birth to the children during 7777 years. They did not know the death [The examples from Gazakh, 2012:12]. M.Ekiji notes that heroes appear in leadership traits in their communities and are described as "ideal type" or "model type" with leadership traits they possess [Ekiji, 2013:16]. The society in which Adam and Eve existed for some time consisted of just two people. The unusual interpretations of the ancient people about growth and birth determined their mythological way of thinking. For some time the existence of only two people in the world in which they lived – Adam and Eve – was an artistic product of the same way of thinking.

The belief that the first human being was born from water and that they were created from water by the will of the Gods, is found both in the mythology of countries around the world and in Turkic creation myths (for the example, one can look at the illustrations from the Turkic epic "Genesis"). In this context, the value of the soil – the earth, as the source of creation makes it have a greater weight than other objects. In Azerbaijani folklore texts there is almost no alternative to the connection of the first human with the soil.

According to the mythological thoughts, it is no coincidence that the birth of Adam and Eve into life, considered the first people, is associated precisely with the soil, which is a symbol of fertility. Sometimes even special rituals were held so that the growth power of the soil could miraculously pass to human: "The wedding night of a young family was held on a new plantation; it was believed that this ritual had a positive effect on the fertility of the soil and it was also believed that this effect would create the opposite effect; Mother Earth had passed on her miraculous power for the birth of a child to those who had just started to make a family" [Pushkina, www.ruthenia.ru].

Talking about the options for the emergence of the first people in Azerbaijani folklore, it is important to refer to the theoretical ideas and practical examples (with the help of folklore texts) about the role of the

Earth - as the mother's womb. Analyzing the motif of birth in folklore, L.A.Sedov also noted that, the miraculous birth was associated with those objects that symbolize fertility in some way [Myths of the peoples of the world, 1988: 385-387]. If we determine this thesis ("formula") to the content of the anthropogenic myths, it is understood that the myth that the first conscious creatures originated precisely from the soil promotes precisely the symbol of fertility in its content. Our conclusion is that although the creation of the first people, according to the ancient beliefs, took place with the power of Allah, the Earth also acted here symbolically in the image of the mother's womb. In addition, there is little information about the anthropomorphic nature of the Earth – the soil in the texts of myths collected from the other Turkic peoples (Altai, yakut), which were about the mythological creature called Mother Earth. Patronizing the women, supporting birth and growth especially, it appears in the role of the image of the Earth – the soil. In fact, although there are images close to the spirit of the Azerbaijani Turks, the name of Mother Earth is not found among the collected folklore texts. But the expression "Mother Earth", told by the people, seems to have approached the essence of the matter. One of the interesting information is that the Turkic peoples imagined the land as the mother of the brave, who gave him strength. "Of course, such thinking is connected with the belief that the land is the initial beginning, echoing with the perception of the land as the first element"[Seyidov, 1989: 304]. According to the mythological ideas, the soil becomes moist after it rains, then the possibility of becoming a mother arises after fertilization has occurred. In folk beliefs, the Earth was considered the fertility God and thus personified the female origin of the universe [Pushkina, www.ruthenia.ru].

One of the texts about the creation of the human (it is seen here that the Earth-soil is anthropomorphic in nature) in the 3rd volume of the series "Karabakh: folklore is also a history" it is said that, the soil itself is also a living being: "Allah bəndəni yaratmaq isdiyirmiş. Onun özünün neçə dənə mələyi varmış. O mələklərdən hangisini göndərişə, yerdən torpağ gətir, torpağ qışqır. Heş biri gətirə bilməyif. Yenəndə torpağ elə vahimə çıxardıf ki, mənə götürmə. Axırda bu mələklərin heş biri yaratmır, Allah Azreyili çağırır. Deyir ki, get torpaxdan bir az götür gəl. Deyir: "Qurban olum, axı bir belə mələklər gedib torpaxdan götürə bilməyif. Torpax vahimə çıxardır ki, mənəndə götürməyin, yaralamayın mənə". Torpax da özü bir cannıdı. Axırı Allah-tala əmr eliyir ki, mən saa deyirəm, get götür gəl. Azreyil yenir torpağın üsdünə. Torpax vahiməsini qaldırır, çığırır, bağırır: "Yox, maa toxunma, mənə yaralama". Deyir: "Ə, sənəndə aparıramsa, saa qayıdacağ". Onçun görürsən, deyir, insan torpaxdan yaranıf, torpağa da qismət olacağ. Get indi yüzillik, minillik qəbri aç, gör orda bir şey qalıb? Torpağ oluf, çıxıf gedif. Onnan sora torpax rahatçılıx tapıf. Deyif ki, əgər maa qayıdacaxsa, olar " (Translation: Allah wanted to create a human. He had many angels. Allah sent his angels to bring some soil, but the Earth did not agree and cried out. No angel has

been able to bring the soil. At the end, Allah calls Azrael. Allah says to go to take some soil and to come back. Azrael answers: "After all, no angel has been able to go and take the soil. The Earth does not allow and cries, says not to injure her". The soil is also alive in itself. In the end, Allah commands: "I tell you, go, take the soil and return back". Azrael comes to the Earth. The Earth falls into panic, raises its voice, screams, yells: "Oh no, don't touch me, don't injure me". But Azrael says: "If I take away 1 handful of soil from you, it will return to you, be sure". Therefore, they say that a person was formed from the soil and will return to the soil, too. Go and open a hundred-year-old, thousand-year-old graves now, see if anything is left there? They have become the soil and have gone". After that, the Earth calms down. It says, "If the soil you took will come back to me, then you can take it" [Karabakh: folklore is also a history, 2012:5]. This version, the theme reflecting the creation of the first human, was told by T.Suleymanov who lived in Jabrayil region and then settled in a refugee town. In this text, the narrator expresses his attachment to the land [Seyidov, 1989: 304], imagining it as a source of strength of his belief that he hopes to return to his occupied land¹ is also in the center of the attention. The other side of the issue is that, in the text in which the narrator telling "if it will return to me" expresses the terms of the land - the Earth, there are features related to mythical thought, in addition to the artistic poetic features. According to these thoughts, the death is not the end, but rather a return to the womb of the land – the Earth, and so, the beginning of a new life [Pushkina, www.ruthenia.ru]. In this case, if we have said such a statement, we'll assume that it is not a false conclusion: Thus, it is also possible to connect the origin of reincarnation (rebirth, resurrection), the main idea of myth texts and considered the archaic beliefs, to primitive ideas based on the creation of the first people from the soil. From time to time, these ideas manifest themselves in the epic folklore texts in the form of revival – destruction – return to oneself – restoration. According to R.Aliyev's thought, this picture is also one of the forms of the idea that "it will return to the land formed from the land" [Aliyev, 2006: 25]. In another myth, which is essentially close to the one we mentioned above, Gayomard puts seed into the soil before the death. After that seed has been in the sunlight for 40 years, the bushes are formed from it. These bushes turn into the human form. Mashya and Mashyana were the first ancestors of the people [Goyyalli, 2015: 180].

It is interesting that the myths about the first human were "transformed into the epic texts at the level of mythological images and motifs" [Gurbanov, 2011:121], it continues to be told today. As studying the texts, we come to the conclusion that although this information is mixed in the memory of the narrator, the

initial semantics, the initial mold, still remain. For example, "the presence of the archaic elements does not reflect the period of creation of these texts, which is found in some folklore examples collected today about Adam and Eve. The problem is that the texts created in the modern era were also written down based on three types of memory that have filtered down from the ancient times - the memory of oral tradition, the memory of the plot and the memory of the narrator" [Asgar, 2013: 107]: "Azrayıldı, Mikayıldı, Cəbrayıldı, İsrəfildı, bular dörd qardaşdı. Adəm peyğəmbər yarananda Allah-talanın hökmünən hərəsi dünyanın bir küncünən bir xışma torpax gətirir. Deyir ki, get dünyanın dörd küncünən torpax gətir, buna can verim. Odur ki, deyillər Adəm torpaxdan yaranıf. Olar dördü də məlakədi. Deyillər: "Yarəbbi, icazə ver biz gedəh gətirəh". Dedi: "Axı gətirəmməzsiniz". Dedi: "Gətirməsəh, bizə nə qəsd eliyirisən elə". Oların dördü də gedillər. Dünyanın dörd küncünən hərəsi bir ovuc torpax gətirir. Qatır o palçığa, Allah-talanın əmriynən buna can gəlir. Dedi: "Yarəbbi, buları gətirdih, bizə hörmətin nə olajax?" Dedi: "Sizə hörmətim odu ki, bütün bu dünyanı sizə tapşırıram" (Translation: "They are four brothers: Azrael, Michael, Gabriel, Israfil. When the Prophet Adam was born, all of them brought a handful of soil from the corner of the world by the command of Allah. Allah says that go and bring the soil from the four sides of the world and I'll give him a soul. That is why they say that Adam was born from the soil. All of them are angels. The brothers say: "Allah, let's go and bring the soil". Allah answers: "You can't bring". The brothers answer: "If we don't bring the soil, do what you like". All of them leave. They bring a handful of soil from four corners of the world and mix it with the same mud. With Allah's command the soil becomes alive. They say: "Almighty Allah, we brought it, how will you respect to us?" Allah answered: "My respect to you is that I entrust this whole world to you") [Karabakh: folklore is also a history, 2012:10].

In this text, which is given as an example, the mythical views about the creation of the human and religious views have joined. In fact, in Islamic cosmogony the creation of human is not presented in this way. In this aspect, the text shows that the ancient myths were later transformed into Islamic values... It means, this text appeared in Karabakh before the Islamic religion, in the age of myth and subsequently underwent transformative changes that we see with the conversion of people to Islam [Gasimova, 2021: 155].

In the other text collected from the region it is said: "Bizim əjdadımız Adəm atadı. Onu torpaxdan qayırıflar. Özü də çox köntöy qayırımışdar. Görüflər ki, çox yoğundu, başdıyıflar bunu yonmağa. Yonduxca bunun yonqarın ənə atımıyflar. Bir yerə topluyufllar. Bu yonqardan mal düzəldifllər. Adam atanın da yetmiş iki uşağı oluf" (Translation: *Our ancestor is Father Adam. He was created from the soil. But he was also*

¹ Jabrayil is one of the territories belonging to the Karabakh region in the Republic of Azerbaijan. In 1993, it was illegally occupied by the Armed Forces of the Republic of Armenia. The narrator, who spoke the well-known text, was a resident of Jabrayil for many years and became a refugee from his permanent place of residence as a result of the invasion. His

mythical way of thinking reflects the sacredness of the soil and the philosophy of an extraordinary love for it. The boundless commitment of the compatriots who were expelled from their homeland – from their sacred lands-to the Karabakh space and the desire to fight for it is also born from this philosophy.

made very roughly. They saw that it was very thick, so they began to carve it. As they carved it, they did not throw away the excess. They gathered it together. They made a cow from that carved part. Father Adam also had seventy-two children). If we pay attention, we will see that in this text the creation of people and the creation of animals are in unity. The animals were created after human (Father Adam or people) [Gasimova, 2021: 155].

In general, analyzing the origin myths the following conclusion was reached: In origin myths the human-tree, human-bird and human-animal kinship is preserved in the form of people transforming into these inanimate-animate beings in origin myths [Bayat, 2007: 200]. It is a logical approach, if we apply this “logical formula” from the land to the native-origin motif, the formula will look as if it has fallen into its own mold; The human, created by Allah from the soil (clay, mud, etc.), is buried in the ground so that he will eventually turn into the soil; because his “dough is kneaded from the soil”. However, the proverb “their soil is taken from one place”, which is very functional in Azerbaijan and is said about husband and wife [Proverbs, p. 608] also mentions the details of the motif Adam-Eve. Even the worship of trees, which is observed in the texts, the belief in the magical power of every fruit, vegetable, cereal plant cultivated in the soil and the roots of such beliefs are measured by the fertility power of the soil and the Earth.

As it is seen, the anthropogonic myths of our national folklore show the logic that Adam was both the first human and the first prophet. It is clear from the examples that the Azerbaijani Turks, like the peoples of the world, believe in the existence of Angels named Jibril, Israfil, Michael, who are the messengers of Allah in connection with the original creation, they also have an idea of Satan, who led them astray at the time of creation. The interesting aspect of the issue is that in some texts spoken by Azerbaijanis, Satan is also described as a creator. We get to know the following text through the book of the Western Azerbaijan folklore, published in 2023: “*Şeytan Adəm peyğəmbərin torpağını, palçığını Məkgədən götürüb. Orda palçıxdan bir insan düzəldib, yer üzünə görə. Onun mələkləri vardı. Hazır olub deyəndə Allah-tala ona nəfəs, ruh, can verir*” (Translation: *Satan took Prophet Adam’s soil and mud from Mecca. He made a man out of the mud for the Earth. He had angels. When he says it is ready, Allah gives him breath, spirit, soul*) [Western Azerbaijan folklore, 2023, volume 1: 26].

The scene of expulsion from the Paradise is also one of the main parts of the Azerbaijani texts in the plot about the subject. As a result of the research carried out by us while preparing this article is that Allah, who created the first human and gave him life, expelled Adam and Eve from the Paradise because they ate the forbidden fruit (according to the texts we studied the names of apple, wheat and barley are mentioned) [Karabakh: folklore is also a history, 2013:15-16]. The function of protection fades into the background and as a punishment the people begin to be endowed with “bearing a child, giving birth, the transition from creation to birth”

[Bayat, 2007: 113]. The conclusion, that we had examining exclusively Azerbaijani folklore texts, is that with the transition from eternity to mortality, the presentation of Allah protecting his human with an anthropomorphic image began to be limited. Of course, this is not to mention the idea of Allah’s deus-otiosus character. We are talking about the fact that, as it is mentioned above, protectiveness has not melted and disappeared at all, since anthropomorphizing is limited. On the contrary, according to the archaic beliefs, blessings, applause, sacrifices, Allah again listened to the desires and aspirations of people and rewarded the grateful people.

Mentioning the name of Father Adam in the first labor songs, which were the relics of the ancient thinking in Azerbaijani folklore, proves once again that the name of the first human who was born miraculous continues to be mentioned in many moments:

“*Adəm ata gələndə,
Qızıl öküz duranda,
Qızıl buğda bitəndə,
Dünya binnət olanda,
Musa çoban olanda,
Şişliyimiz erkəcdi*” [Songs, beliefs, applause, 1986: 32]

(Translation: *When Father Adam came, When the golden bull stands, When the golden wheat is green, When the world is funny, When Moses was a shepherd, The meat for our kebab is from male sheep*”).

The name of Adam is also observed in another song:

“*Bu saya yaxşı saya
Həm çeşməyə, həm çaya
Həm Ülkərə, həm Aya
Həm yoxsula, həm baya.
Bu saya kimdən qaldı?
Adəm atadan qaldı*” [Songs, beliefs, applause, 1986: 32].

(Translation: *This sheep is a good sheep, To the spring and the river, To the star and the Moon, To the poor and the rich. Who inherited this sheep? Adam inherited it from his father*).

The content of anthropogonic myths can also be observed in ashik poetry:

“*Adəm ki yedi buğdanı
Bir görün nə etdilər
Ol xudadan əmr olundu
Sərəndibə atdılar
Adəmnən Hənvə ana
Bir-birini tapdılar
Hənvə doxsan oğlan doğdu
Gərđişi- dövrəna bax*” [Ashiq Ali, 2006: 120].

(Translation: *Adam ate the wheat, Look, what they did. Allah ordered, Adam and Mother Eve were thrown to Sarandib and they met each other. Eve gave birth to ninety sons, Look at the current period*).

Another version of the poem was found in the work of the poet Mammadhuseyn, who lived in the same period with Ashiq Ali:

“*Şeytan yedirdi buğdanı
Adəmə nə etdilər;
Ol xudadan əmr olundu
Sərəndibə atdılar*”

Adəm ilə Həvva ana

Bir-biriylə yatdılar

Həvva doxsan oğul doğdu,

Gərđişi-dövrana bax" [Selections from Azerbaijani ashii poetry, 2005: 258]

(Translation: *Satan forced Adam to eat wheat, so what did they do to him? The order was made by Allah and they were thrown to Sarandib. Adam and Mother Eve slept together. Eve gave birth to ninety sons, Look at the current period*).

It should be noted that the place Serendib mentioned above according to the Islamic worldview, is the territory of India where Allah sent Adam down [Aliyev -Ayvazli, 2017: 48].

Thus, one can conclude: according to the mythical ideas, Adam and Eve, considered the ancestors of humans, were miraculously created and from time to time with the help of these ideas the male-female relationships were made artistic and reflected in more poetic descriptions of the creation of human. The idea that began with the soil laid the foundation for the belief in the possibility of creation from the inanimate objects. However, majority of Azerbaijani folklore examples are the samples in which the mentioned beliefs (from the proverbs to the epics) are widely covered, narrated in a simple and clear form, expressing symbolic birth – creation by style, narration, means of description. It is also observed that in these examples, the ideas about the origin of the first human or people existing in myths serve as the basis for the emergence of some folklore motifs, especially the motif of miraculous birth. However, the myths that describe the creation of the first human precisely from the soil are perfected and form the core of the motif of the miraculous birth and retain their sacredness. The thoughts told by F.Bayat about it also look attractive: "As the first creation is sacred, it also serves as the beginning of subsequent ones" [Bayat, 2007:77]. In short, due to this logic, the following idea is realized: the birth from the different things such as water, wood, any fruit, a mountain or a stone, etc. has a direct connection with the emergence from the soil. The signs of this connection are also presented solemnly in the rituals of Azerbaijani Turks. "The soil has an extremely important position as the material basis of human creation. It also has sacral mythological semantics, proceeding from the fact that it is the material basis of creation. The mythical roots of the awakening of the soil in spring are also associated with the concept of resurrection and revival. However, it is sourced due to the myth of human creation" [Novruz holiday and Tuesdays, www.kayzen.az].

Let's accept that the Azerbaijani Turks were able to illuminate the miracle of creation from the soil in their folklore, referring to the content of various heavenly religions, but it is also a fact that the belief of the soil living in the mythical thought of the people was immortalized and transported to its ceremonies and preserved its peculiarity. The solemnity of Earth Tuesday is very different from the solemnity of other Tuesdays. Sometimes Earth Tuesday is called "Last Tuesday" or

"Earth Tuesday"², "with its unique rituals and ceremonies it becomes more different than others... The soil is cared for with special love" [Goyyalli, 2015: 182]. But it proves that it became sacred, becoming a symbol of both fertility and miraculous creation.

Conclusion: It is also important from the point of view of world and Turkic mythology to investigate the folklore texts reflecting the thoughts of Azerbaijanis about the creation of the first people. The scene of a conscious being opening the eyes to the world is among the uniquely described texts of Azerbaijani folklore.

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² It is one of the special days solemnly celebrated on the eve of Novruz holiday, which is held on the occasion of the arrival of spring. On Tuesday, which comes before the 20th or 21st

of March, bonfires are lit, national dishes and sweets are baked, the children walking from door to door are given shares.

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